

CAPABLE

CAnCer PAtients Better Life Experience

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1. Versions History

Version	Date	Author	Comments
1.0	02/06/2022	Ella Barkan	Initial document
2.0	24/06/2022	Ella Barkan	Document before internal review
3.0	03/07/2022	Ronald Cornet	Internal Review
4.0	06/07/2022	Ella Barkan	Updates after Internal Review
5.0	07/07/2022	Silvana Quaglini	Final Review
6.0	10/07/2022	Ella Barkan	Final Version

2. Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to demonstrate the capabilities of statistical-based components that support users of the DSS (Decision Support System) that is part of AI framework in CAPABLE architecture. This demonstration involves CAPABLE components from two groups: knowledge-based components which is Infographics Model and data-driven components which are Statistical Summarizer and Population Prediction Models. Demonstrations of both groups are present. The **Demonstration of Statistical Summarizer and Population Prediction Models** is presented as a video and includes all the steps in data analysis, model development, and evaluation for the survival outcome. Voice-over and a walk-through in this document explain all steps of the demonstration. **Demonstration of Infographics Model** is presented as a collection of the developed educational aids that are going to help physicians in discussions with patients, and a mockup of integration of most recent clinical summaries related to treatment decisions into the physician DSS.

The document is organized in the following way:

Section 3 provides a brief overview of the AI framework and its components, healthcare professionals (HCPs)' needs for statistical-based decision support, and the implementation of these needs by corresponding components in the AI framework.

Section 4 presents the **Demonstration of Infographics Model**. The section includes an overview of the component and knowledge sources description. Through generated infographics, we will see how component helps physicians discuss treatment side-effects with patients and provides them with the most recently updated summaries from publications related to outcomes and toxicities of the different treatment types

Section 5 presents the **Demonstration of Statistical Summarizer and Population Prediction Models**. A brief overview of components and data sources is provided. The detailed presentation of these components in action is provided by a demo that applied to the prediction of 3-year survival of Metastatic Renal Cell Carcinoma patients starting their first systemic treatment. In addition, we provide summaries on the status of all other models developed for the rest of the required outcomes.

3. Statistical-based decision component as a part of AI framework

The AI framework is a part of the CAPABLE system architecture and was presented in D5.2 (Gilboa-Solomon, 2021). The aim of the AI framework is to provide support for both patients' and physicians' needs. The framework is defined as a set of concepts, libraries, tools, practices, and methodologies that cover formal knowledge representation, logic-based reasoning, and machine learning techniques.

The overview of the AI framework can be found in **Figure 3.1**. It can be seen that all components can be grouped into two categories:

- (1) Low-level (back-end) components that include knowledge-driven models such as plan models, ontological models, and rule-based/algorithmic models; and data-driven models such as population-based risk predictive models and personalized predictive models, as well as statistical summaries on data;
- (2) High-level (closer to front-end) components: they deliver support to the physician and patient, and offer hybrid support that combines knowledge and data-driven techniques.

All low-level components are developed based on two main sources: (a) Real World Data (RWD): Patient data coming from Electronic Health Records (EHR), sensors, and questionnaires, including patient-reported outcomes (PROs); (b) Knowledge captured in scientific publications, clinical guidelines, standard terminologies, and educational materials.

This document and the demonstrations will present the backend components responsible for the statistical decision. A red outline in **Figure 3.1** marks these components and their related data sources and knowledge. It can be seen that these components correspond to both groups: knowledge-driven and data-driven modules. Therefore we will provide two demonstrations in sections 4 and 5 correspondingly.

The outcomes of these components will be accessible through the user interface (UI) component of the Physician DSS. This module, which provides tools for patient management for HCPs using evidence-based models (Computer-Interpretable Guidelines, CIGs), will augment the interface with infographics, statistical summaries, and outcomes of population-based prediction models that should help physicians with patients' management decisions.

The need for statistical-based decision components for HCPs and patients in the CAPABLE system was defined during the summarization of interviews and questionnaires in NKI and ICSM. There are two requirements involving statistical-based support (full details can be found in section 5 of D2.1 (Peleg, 2020)):

- HCPs are often involved in complex decision-making regarding treatment for patients. There is a need for supportive tools to facilitate this complex decision-making, for example, treatment choices, survival, and immune-related adverse events.

- Patients indicated varying levels of satisfaction with the information currently provided by their respective healthcare professionals. Patients are interested in a wide range of topics, including their diagnosis, treatments, and side effects.

More details about relations between CAPABLE users' requirements and the responsible components can be found in Table 5.2.2 in D5.2 (Gilboa-Solomon, 2021)

Figure 3.1. Overview of the AI framework

4. Demonstration of knowledge-driven summaries

4.1. Overview

As described in deliverables D2.1 (Peleg, 2020) and D5.2 (Gilboa-Solomon, 2021), we have previously identified relevant information needs of clinicians and patients to be supported by the CAPABLE dashboard and app. Healthcare professionals and patients have indicated the need for clinical decision aids and educational aids for discussing the diagnosis, treatments, prognosis and side-effects. In the following development period, in discussion with healthcare professionals, we've determined to focus on infographics suitable to be viewed by patients on their own or to be shown by clinicians during consultations. The topics of the infographics were selected from the extensive information needs list described in D2.1 (Peleg, 2020). As a significant component of the CAPABLE patient app is symptom reporting, we decided to focus on infographics related to immunotherapy adverse events. Currently developed infographics include:

- Types of treatment for melanoma patients
 - Different types of systematic treatment options
- Immunotherapy
 - General information
 - Process of immunotherapy infusion
- Immunotoxicity
 - What symptoms should patients be on the look-out for
 - Occurrence of adverse events
 - Fatigue and self-care tips
 - Skin side-effects and self-care tips
 - Diarrhea and self-care tips
 - Nausea and self-care tips
 - Fever and self-care tips

While developing these infographic aids, we took recommendations into consideration from Trevena et al. (2013) and Bonna et al. (2021), describing the current best practice for presenting probabilities and quantitative information in patient decision aids.

4.2. Knowledge Sources

We have performed a literature review and generated a report that summarizes the relations between biomarkers and the outcomes (response, survival, and toxicity) for patients with high-risk and advanced melanoma treated with immunotherapy. This report with a review can be found in **Annex 1**. In addition, this report with a review may be provided directly to the clinicians in the clinician dashboard in order to help them with the treatment-related decisions. In **Annex 2**, we show a mockup of the possible way of the report integration into the physician DSS interface.

In addition, we've used the ESMO Toxicities from Immunotherapy, ESMO patient guide Immunotherapy Side effects, and internal patient guides from NKI to develop the patient-friendly infographics.

4.3. Demonstration of Infographics

In this subsection, we will demonstrate the infographics that are generated to help physicians to hold discussions with patients about treatment choice, the process of treatment, and the possible side-effects and their management and tips for the patients.

These infographics will be integrated in the CAPABLE patient app, to be viewed by patients on their own, and in the clinician dashboard to be shown and discussed with by clinicians during consultations. Some of the infographics are specific for a cancer type, others are general.

4.3.1. Infographic for discussion of treatment and types of immunotherapy treatment

Targeted therapy or immunotherapy? For stage 4 melanoma

Several treatments are available for stage 4 melanoma.

Aim of the treatments: ensure that the metastases stop growing or preferably become smaller, which also reduces the symptoms.

The proposed treatment by the doctor depends on a number of things:

- how many metastases you have and how big they are
- Where the metastases are
- How fast the tumour(s) are growing
- the LDH level in your blood: this tells you something about how aggressive or extensive the melanoma is
- the genetic characteristics of the tumour
- your condition
- Your own preferences

Potential treatment options:

Immunotherapy

Targeted therapy

(Palliative) radiation

Systematic treatment options for patients with inoperable metastatic melanoma

Currently, there are two types of systemic therapy for people with metastatic inoperable melanoma: **targeted therapy** and **immunotherapy**. Targeted therapy is only available to a group of patients.

Targeted therapy

About half of the people with metastatic melanoma have a mutation in the BRAF gene. A gene is a piece of DNA that has a specific function.

A mutation in the BRAF gene can cause cells to divide uncontrollably. This is how a melanoma occurs.

There is a special treatment available for this mutation: targeted therapy. After DNA analysis of the tumour, it becomes clear whether you also have this mutation. And whether targeted therapy with BRAF/MEK inhibitors could be a treatment for you.

DNA analysis of the tumour

4.3.2. Infographic about the process of immunotherapy infusions

What does the day of immunotherapy infusion look like?

Blood testing

Weighing & check vital signs

Visit with nurse practitioner

Immunotherapy infusion

Observation

What is the timing of administering the infusion and the observation period?

First infusion

60 minutes per infusion

60 minutes observation

Second infusion

30 minutes per infusion

30 minutes observation

Other infusions

30 minutes per infusion

4.3.3. Infographics to discuss risks of side-effects for patients on ipilimumab, nivolumab and combination therapy (ipilimumab and nivolumab)

What symptoms should I look out for?

General
Fatigue is a common side effect in patients treated with checkpoint inhibitors. Although its cause is poorly understood, it is important to exclude thyroid, pituitary, and other endocrine disorders.

Skin
Extensive rash or itching.

Gastrointestinal:
Diarrhoea especially containing blood or mucus, or severe abdominal pain.

Endocrine:
Fatigue, weight loss, nausea/vomiting, excessive thirst or appetite, excessive and/or frequent urination.

Respiratory:
Shortness of breath, cough.

Any of these less common symptoms:

- headache.
- confusion.
- muscle weakness or pain.
- numbness.
- painful or swollen joints.
- unexplained fever.
- tendency to bruise easily.
- loss of vision.

Immunotherapy side-effects

Side-effects from immunotherapy can affect any organ or tissue, but most commonly affect the skin, colon, lungs, liver and endocrine organs (such as the pituitary gland or thyroid gland).

Most immune-related side effects are mild to moderate and reversible if detected early and addressed appropriately.

You should always mention any symptoms that are worrying you - as soon as you notice them - to your oncology team.

They will be monitoring your progress and testing your blood for signs of any side-effects without obvious symptoms in their early stages.

Endocrine organs
e.g., underactive or overactive thyroid, or inflammation of the pituitary gland (hypophysitis)

Liver
e.g., liver inflammation (hepatitis)

Skin
e.g., rash, itching, or loss of pigment

Lungs
e.g., lung inflammation (pneumonitis)

Gastro-intestinal tract
e.g., diarrhoea, colitis

Occurrence of side-effects in patients on ipilimumab

Fatigue: ~40%

Rash: ~40%

Itching: ~25-35%

Gastro-intestinal side-effects, usually diarrhoea: ~30%

Hormonal gland disorders: less than ~8%

Hepatitis (liver inflammation): 5-10%

Fatigue and self-care tips

The Treatment can make you tired. The most common complaints are

- having a constant feeling of exhaustion
- physical and/or mental exertion takes more effort
- a (great) lack of energy, you think you can't do anything anymore
- irritability
- emotional instability, mood swings
- lack of interest in your surroundings
- sleepiness and listlessness

The fatigue symptoms may persist for a long time after the treatment. Sometimes a few months, sometimes even years. The fatigue can be caused by physical, psychological and emotional conditions.

Tips:

Move as much as possible to prevent your condition from deteriorating.

Consider exercising under the supervision of a physiotherapist.

Get a good night's sleep, keep set times for going to bed and getting up.

Your energy is precious, use it carefully. Decide for yourself what you want to spend your energy on

If necessary, ask for help from family or friends, or call in home care.

Do fun and relaxing things in time.

Gastro-intestinal side-effects and self-care tips - diarrhoea

Immunotherapy can cause gastrointestinal complaints, usually diarrhoea.

This varies from mild to sometimes very severe (water-thin, many times a day) and may be accompanied by bleeding. Sometimes, a severe inflammation of the intestine that cannot be controlled by drug treatment. In these cases, surgical removal of (part of) the colon is necessary.

All other cases of diarrhoea have been successfully treated by stopping immunotherapy treatment and/or by treatment with anti-diarrhoea medicines, corticosteroids (mostly prednisone) or other medicinal treatments.

Tips:

Drink water or sports drinks regularly to ensure you get enough fluids (at least 1.5 to 2L)

Eat food low in fat and fibre such as: pasta, white bread or rice; lean meat (turkey, chicken)

The mucous membrane of the sphincter may be irritated by frequent diarrhoea. Use soft toilet paper. Zinc oxide ointment may help to protect the skin in case of irritation.

What to avoid:

Foods that increase bowel movements: large and high-fat meals; alcohol (beer, wine); caffeine-containing drinks (coffee, chocolate); foods with coarse fibres, seeds or pits (wholemeal bread); nuts

Foods that increase gas formation: onion, leek, cabbage, garlic, paprika, cucumber, melon and carbonated drinks

Foods that irritate the intestinal mucosa: strong herbs and spices

Perfumed wipes

Gastro-intestinal side-effects and self-care tips - nausea

The treatment may cause nausea and vomiting. You may experience the following symptoms:

- gagging and vomiting
- little or no appetite
- stomach complaints, such as feeling full or aching
- abdominal pain or cramps, bloated belly, rumbling in the belly
- thirst

Medicines can reduce or prevent nausea and vomiting. It is important that you always take the medicines as discussed with your doctor. Stick to the fixed times for taking the medicines, even if you are not nauseous.

Tips:

Eat small meals more often. Try to avoid an empty stomach by eating small snacks regularly, such as a cracker, biscuit or a bowl of yoghurt.

Morning sickness sometimes subsides after eating a piece of toast before getting up. In the evening, for example, put a packet of toast next to the bed or a packet with breadsticks and cheese spread.

Drink a lot, at least 1.5 litres a day. This is 14 cups or 12 mugs a day

Try whether drinking carbonated drinks helps, these can help to expel excess air from the stomach, relieving the feeling of fullness. Don't take the drink too cold as this can cause stomach problems again.

Sucking on something makes the salivary glands work. This prevents dry mouth and a foul taste in the mouth. Think of (sugar-free) sour, ice cubes, water ice, soft pieces of fruit and liquorice.

Try dishes that are cold or at room temperature, these are often better tolerated. Let hot foods and drinks cool until they are lukewarm.

If possible, sit up straight during the meal or try to sit with the upper part of your body in an upright position. Do not lie down again immediately after a meal. Sit upright for half an hour after the meal. This allows the meal to sink in better and reduces nausea.

Whenever possible, take a short walk outside. This can help to reduce nausea and make eating after a meal matter. Stay out of the kitchen where food has just been prepared and ventilate your home well

Fever and self-care tips

Fever is an increase in the body temperature above 38.5°C. The treatment can cause a fever. This may also occur several days after the immunotherapy infusion.

Tips:

In case of fever, you lose more fluid than usual. Therefore, it is important that you drink enough. Drink 1½ to 2 litres per day; this is 16 cups or 14 mugs per day.

Only on the advice of your doctor, take 2 to 4 tablets (1000 mg) of paracetamol daily against fever.

Skin side-effects and self-care tips

Skin rash is a common side effect in patients treated with immunotherapy.

Most cases have been mild and less than 1% of cases have been severe.

Some patients experienced itching only or had it in combination with the rash. The rash usually goes away after stopping nivolumab, but can be treated additionally with corticosteroid cream and/or desloratadine.

General advice:

Use emollients and protective creams and ointments to keep the skin supple and prevent it from drying out. Symptoms such as itching, scaling, cracking and burning are reduced by these products. They are available without a prescription.

Protect yourself properly from the sun, wind and cold to prevent the skin from drying out.

Tips for rash:

Use an oily cream as soon as you suffer from dry skin. Dry skin is also more likely to cause itching.

Tips for itching:

Cut your nails very short and keep them clean.

Take into account that itching is sometimes aggravated by heat or by contact with clothing or bedding.

5. Demonstration of data-driven statistical analysis and prediction models

5.1. Overview

Data-driven components that provide statistical-based decision support include “Statistical Summarizer” and “Population Prediction Models”. Both of them use Retrospective Data for generation summaries and models.

Statistical summaries are static findings from the analysis that provide concise characteristics of the processed data, like descriptive statistics and univariate analysis, however, they do not allow for deriving patient-specific recommendations.

Prediction models are executable findings from the analysis that can be applied to new patients in order to provide insights related to clinical treatment, such as response to treatment, survival, and toxicity.

Retrospective data is used to develop population-based prediction models and summaries. We will run the developed prediction models on the common structured data from EHR, which is part of the prospective data (collected during CAPABLE pilot), and summarize the results. As was already mentioned in D5.2, the population-based predictive models and summaries are based on small retrospective data sets, have no FDA/CE approval to be used in clinical practice, and will not be part of the prospective study (for those legal constraints). The conclusions of these prediction models will be provided in a report to the physicians in a statistical manner, with no personal advice per patient.

More details about Retrospective Predictive Models and Statistical Summaries components can be found in D5.2 (Gilboa-Solomon, 2021) sections 7.1.2.1 and 7.1.4.2 respectively

5.2. Data Sources

5.2.1. Retrospective Data

The retrospective data is EHR-based structured clinical data of the patients collected for two types of cancers (Melanoma, Renal Cancer) in two hospitals in the Netherlands and Italy. The melanoma data set comprises 500 patients in stages III and IV from NKI in Amsterdam treated (in 560 lines) with Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors (ICI): anti-PD1 antibodies (Nivolumab, Pembrolizumab) alone or combined with anti-CTLA4 antibodies (Ipilimumab). The data set of renal cancer includes 343 patients with mRCC (metastatic Renal Cell Carcinoma) collected from Italian hospitals and managed by ICS Maugeri. The data set includes 917 treatment lines with up to 7 treatment lines available per patient, where the majority of treatments (~90%) are molecularly targeted agents. Subjects in both data sets are presented with demographic details, diagnostic information, and clinical details collected before the treatment start, like metastases status, blood tests, patient condition, and treatment details. As well, patient-level (survival) and treatment-level (response, toxicities, and the reason for treatment termination) outcomes are included in these data sets.

Full data details can be found in Section 8.4, Figures 8.4.1-8.4.3 of D2.1 (Peleg, 2020), Section 3.2 of D5.1 (Barkan, 2020), and Section 6.2 of D5.2 (Gilboa-Solomon, 2021).

5.2.2. IBM MarketScan Research Databases

This is a set of databases of insurance claims compiled from health insurers, large employers, and government programs in the USA (<https://www.ibm.com/il-en/products/marketscan-research-databases>)

This data set includes subsets of Melanoma and mRCC with 1800 and 2400 patients respectively, passing the similar treatment but missing most of the diagnostic and clinical characteristics available in our retrospective data. On the other hand, this data set has rich information about diagnoses, procedures, and drugs and can be explored for other cancer-related tasks. Our initial exploration was on predicting renal cancer using patients' comorbidities. The summary of this initial work is described in **Annex 3**. For future work, we will continue this exploration of this task using modern AI techniques and continue checking the possibilities of utilization of this data for improving predictive models developed for CAPABLE tasks.

5.3. Demonstration of statistical analysis and predictive models for survival prediction of mRCC patients

We are going to demonstrate the work of statistical analysis and predictive models applied to the task of predicting 3-year overall survival for patients with Metastatic Renal Cell Carcinoma starting their first systemic treatment. The full version of this demonstration can be found in the following [link](#). The demonstration is constructed as a slideshow with explanations and includes the running of Python and R notebooks.

5.3.1. Goals of the study

We defined the next goals for the study:

- To investigate the prognosis of patients starting first-line of systemic treatment for better management and decision-making in clinical practice
- Achieve the best performance for predictive models using State-Of-The-Art AI methods and tools
- Use and potentially contribute to open source packages (FuseMedML, 2022)

5.3.2. Study Design and Patients Data

As presented in **Figure 5.3.2.1**, this retrospective study included patients in Italy with mRCC who underwent systemic treatment between 2004 and 2019. In the study, 21 patients were excluded from the cohort of 343 originally collected patients as some were not verified and some were censored, reducing the final data set to 322 patients. Statistical and survival analyses were applied to all patients in the data set, resulting in the detection of significant prognostic factors. Prior to the development of predictive models, the cohort was split into two mutually exclusive sets. We assigned 80% of the patients to a training set, which was used for model generation. The remaining 20% of the data was defined as a hold-out.

We evaluated the developed models in a five-fold cross-validation on the training data set and on the hold-out data. We compared the performance of the developed model with the performance of four well-known models applied to our data set for survival prognosis.

Figure 5.3.2.2 demonstrates the main groups of patient details available in the data set for the baseline and follow-up periods. For model development, we used patient details collected at the baseline period before treatment started.

Figure 5.3.2.1 Study Design

Figure 5.3.2.2 Patients Characteristics

5.3.3. Statistical and Survival Analysis

Statistical and survival analyses were demonstrated as running R notebooks in the attached video. The resulting tables are attached in **Annex 4**. Statistical Analysis included: (1) Descriptive Statistics with verification balancing train and hold-out data sets split; results are presented in **Table 8.4.1** (2) Univariate Analysis of all characteristics with respect to 3-year survival outcome, results are presented in **Table 8.4.2**. In statistical analysis, for continuous variables, the data were presented as median and interquartile range (IQR), and for categorical variables, as frequencies (%). We conducted a Wilcoxon rank sum or Chi-square-square test and Fisher's test to compare continuous or categorical variables, respectively. Summarizing the results of the descriptive statistics, we can see that 79% of patients were less than 65 years old and 78% of participants were male. Clear cell type was diagnosed in 90% of patients. The median time from diagnosis to the treatment start was 12.8 months. 94% of patients were treated by targeted therapy. Objective response was demonstrated in 39% and high CTCAE grade (≥ 3) adverse events appeared in 36% of patients.

In the univariate analysis we found variables of "Time from diagnosis to treatment start", "Age", "Performance score", "Metastases stage at diagnosis", "Histological Grade", "Sarcomatoid feature", "LDH" and "Hemoglobin" be significant for this test with p-value < 0.001 .

Survival analysis included Kaplan-Meier (Kaplan, 1958) analysis with log-rank test and Univariate Cox proportional hazards models (Cox, 1972) for all patient's characteristics. Results of the survival analysis can be found in **Table 8.4.3**. We can see that 6 variables were found to be significant for both survival analysis methods and for univariate analysis: "Age at diagnosis", "Performance score", "Metastases stage at diagnosis", "Sarcomatoid feature", "Hemoglobin" and "LDH", with p-value < 0.001 .

5.3.4. Data pre-processing and feature set enrichment

In this data set we are missing values for about 5% of the patients who didn't undergo surgery, and are missing histopathological and staging details. We applied several methods to resolve any missing data, and this allowed us to include all patient details in the model development. One method was based on inference from other variables approved by medical experts where it was possible. The mean imputing was applied for the rest of the variables. Standardization of all variables was done by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance.

With the guidance of our medical partners, we applied type transformation for some of the clinical features. This included: the conversion of categorical features to binary ones by grouping their values (e.g. grouping histological grades to Low and High), continuous variables to indicators (e.g. lab results exceeding the limits), and continuous to categorical (e.g. Tumor size was split to 4 groups).

We enriched our feature set with variables that represent patients' risk scores calculated according to the well-known prognostic models of OS prediction for mRCC. The wide set of clinico-pathological characteristics available in our data set allowed us to generate patient risk scores for the long list of prognostic models. We added five features of risk scores using models that predict OS and progression-free survival (PFS) from the time of RCC diagnosis (blue boxes and models on the left side of **Figure 5.3.4.1**) and four features of risk scores using the models predicting OS from the first-line of systemic treatment for mRCC patients (orange boxes and models on the right side of **Figure 5.3.4.1**)

Figure 5.3.4.1 Feature Set Enrichment

5.3.5. Establishing Model

As mentioned above, we split the data set into the train and hold-out cohorts. To ensure a good balance of patients while splitting a small data set, we used stratification on the outcomes and the top significant features from the univariate analysis. We then verified the feature distribution between the training and hold-out sets using statistical analysis methods (see descriptive statistics table **Table 8.4.1** in **Annex 4**).

We developed the models using a five-fold cross-validation method on the training set. Meaning, four folds for training, one fold for evaluation, five times in a round-robin manner. We used all the features for model development, allowing automatic feature selection in the model. We used state-of-the-art tree-based models: XGBoost (Chen, 2016) and Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), and MLP (Lippmann, 1994) which is a neural net. We applied a grid-search method to determine the optimal parameters for predictive models. Initially, we built the models using these three selected methods. We then combined them in an ensemble by averaging the predictive probabilities of the individual models. Using the ensemble method allowed us to improve the generalization and reduce the variance of the different models, which leads to a more stable and robust final model. The final ensemble model was evaluated on cross-validation and hold-out cohorts. As depicted in **Figure 5.3.5.1**, we generated final prediction probabilities for the hold-out set as averages of the predictions from each of the five models. These prediction averages were further averaged in the ensemble model. For the cross-validation set, we merged the final probabilities of five cross-validation models into one vector before the ensembling stage.

Figure 5.3.5.1 Establishing predictive model

5.3.6. Model Evaluation and Explainability

The final ensemble model was evaluated on cross-validation and hold-out cohorts. The predictive performance of models was quantified using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, and its predictive accuracy was assessed by the area under the ROC curve (AUC) with 95% confidence intervals (Hanley, 1982), and by assessing specificity at high sensitivity levels. The steps of evaluation are presented in **Figure 5.3.6.1** and results of evaluation are demonstrated in **Figure 5.3.6.2**. We can see that ensemble models provide higher or comparable results with individual models. In general, using ensemble model improves generalization and reduces variance of the different models, which leads to a more stable and robust final model. We used Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) (Lundberg, 2017) to understand the machine learning predictive models and to explain feature importance; these demonstrated how each feature of each patient affects the predictive model results. The SHAP summary plot presents features ordered top-down based on their impact on the outcome. The SHAP values of a feature are correlated to the possibility of survival: a positive SHAP value means a positive impact on the prediction, while negative ones lead the model to predict “no survival”. The dot color represents the values that each feature can take: red for high values, blue for low values, and purple for values that are close to the average value. **Figure 5.3.6.1** shows the SHAP explainability for Random Forest. Consider the “Karnofsky PS” feature as an example. We see that this feature is important for the model since it appears in the third position from the top. The higher (red) values of this feature are associated with a higher likelihood of survival. Patients with lower (blue) and average (purple) feature values have a stronger influence on the negative outcome.

Figure 5.3.6.1 Evaluation of predictive model

Figure 5.3.6.2 : Results of comparison of individual models with ensemble model for Cross-validation and Hold-out sets

5.3.7. Comparing with existing models

We compared the performance of the final ensemble model with the performance of four well-known calculators applied to our data set for survival prognosis. Specifically, we carried out comparisons with validated MSKCC (Motzer, 2002), IKCWG (Manola, 2011), validated IMDC (Heng, 2013), and Modified IMDC (M-IMDC) (Tanaka, 2017). See details in **Figure 5.3.7.1**. We compared predictive performance using AUC ROC, as well as with the DeLong test (DeLong, 1988) to assess the significance between two AUCs computed on the same cohort. We also used the McNemar test (McNemar, 1947) to verify the significance of model results at high sensitivity operation points. The results of the latter test are important for models deployed in clinical practice and thus are of special interest. Results of the comparison can be seen in **Figure 5.3.7.2**. It can be seen that the ensemble model outperforms all the other models in both cross-validation and hold-out sets in all applied metrics using AUC and demonstrates good specificity results in high sensitivity operations that is a good criteria for the model's deployment in clinical practice. In addition, we compared the net benefits of the ensemble model with the net benefit of well-known prognostic models using Decision Curve Analysis (DCA) (Vickers, 2006). DCA estimates the net benefit of a model by calculating the weighted difference between the true- and false-positive rates, where weighting between them is done with the odds of the threshold probability of the involved clinical risk. It can be seen in **Figure 5.3.7.3** that the ensemble model has a higher net clinical benefit than all the traditional models and 2 extreme models for cross-validation and hold-out sets. FuseMedML (FuseMedML 2022) open source package was used to perform all the above-mentioned evaluation methods and tests except SHAP and DCA analysis

Figure 5.3.7.1 Comparison with well-known models

Figure 5.3.7.2 : Results of comparison of ensemble model with well-known prognostic models

Figure 5.3.7.3: Results of DCA analysis comparing ensemble model with well-known prognostic models

5.4. Predictive model results for defined outcomes and diseases

The methods demonstrated in Section 5.3 for developing predictive models for 3-year survival of mRCC patients that were described and demonstrated in the previous section can be applied to all defined outcomes in both Renal Cancer and Melanoma data sets: predicting of survival, response, toxicity and the reason for treatment termination

As the first step in this process of model development, we established and evaluated several baseline models for the rest of the defined outcomes. The evaluation was done using the AUC ROC metric in a cross-validation way on the whole data set. **Figures 5.4.1** and **5.4.2** summarize these results. The next steps for the model’s improvement will be using methods presented in the demo.

Prediction Outcome	Logistic Regression	XGBoost	Random Forest
Best response	0.64	0.67	0.68
Toxicity	0.70	0.74	0.75
Reason for treatment stop	0.71	0.68	0.69
2- year overall survival starting ICI treatment	0.67	0.67	0.68

Figure 5.4.1. Evaluation of predictive models (with AUC ROC) for Melanoma data set

Prediction Outcome	Logistic Regression	XGBoost	Random Forest
Best response	0.65	0.64	0.69
Toxicity	0.63	0.60	0.63
Reason for treatment stop	0.62	0.64	0.67

Figure 5.4.2. Evaluation of predictive models (with AUC ROC) for mRCC data set. Results for 3-year survival are provided in section 5.3

6. Glossary

AUC	Area Under the Curve
CIG	Computer-interpretable Clinical Practice Guideline
CTCAE	Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events
DSS	Decision Support System
EHR	Electronic Health Record
HCP	Healthcare Professional
ICSM	Instituto Clinico Scientifico Maugeri hospital
IMDC	International Metastatic renal cell carcinoma Database Consortium
MSKCC	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center
NKI	Netherlands Cancer Institute
UI	User Interface

7. References

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8. Annexes

8.1. Annex 1 - Literature for predicting response and toxicity in patients with high-risk and advanced melanoma treated with immune checkpoint

8.1.1. Overall survival/response

Several studies have shown a correlation between toxicity and ICI response. (Eggermont et al., 2020; Okada et al., 2019). It is suggested that clinical response improves with irAE occurrence.

Hopkins et al. conducted a literature review on routinely available blood and clinical markers associated with treatment response. In summary, they found evidence for the association between a range of factors and improved response or overall survival. An increased (relative) lymphocyte count and increased eosinophil count at baseline was associated with improved overall survival. A lowered neutrophil count, neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio, or monocyte count was associated with improved overall survival. Low lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels at baseline were associated with improved overall survival. In addition, decreased LDH levels at week 12 vs. baseline were associated with worsened overall survival. An ECOG PS score <1 at baseline was associated with longer overall survival. The presence of early irAEs, any grade AEs, or specifically rash or vitiligo was associated with improved overall survival. Table 8.1.1 shows a Table from Hopkins et al. that included studies and their respective results. (Hopkins et al., 2017)

A retrospective analysis among 287 patients with unresectable stage III and stage IV melanoma confirmed by multivariate analysis that normal LDH levels, no brain metastases, ECOG PS 0, and objective response to the treatment were strong predictors of longer overall survival. For progressive-free survival, absence of brain metastases, ECOG 0, and treatment response were found to be predictive factors on multivariate analysis. In addition, median overall survival decreased when treatment lines increased. (Cybulska-Stopa et al., 2020). These results are similar to results found by Diem et al., who also identified elevated LDH and ECOG PS 0 as adverse factors for overall survival. In addition, the number of organs involved was negatively associated with overall survival. (Diem et al., 2015)

Several literature reviews have been done that describe biomarkers potentially associated with ICPI treatment response. (Darvin et al., 2018; Gibney et al., 2016)

Table 8.1.1 Summary of preliminary evidence of routinely available blood and clinical markers predictive of ICI outcomes.

Marker	ICI therapy	N	Study results	Reference
Lymphocyte count	Ipilimumab	51, 73	≥1000 per µl at week 6→↑ OS	(Delyon et al, 2013; Ku et al, 2010)
	Ipilimumab	82, 40	↑ At 2–8 weeks vs baseline→↑ response	(Bjoern et al, 2016; Martens et al, 2016b)
	Ipilimumab	95	↑ At week 12 vs baseline→↑ OS	(Simeone et al, 2014)
	Nivolumab	98	≥1000 per µl at week 3–6→↑ OS	(Nakamura et al, 2016)
Relative lymphocyte count	Ipilimumab	209	↑ Baseline→↑ OS	(Martens et al, 2016a)
	Pembrolizumab	616	↑ Baseline→↑ OS	(Weide et al, 2016)
Total leucocyte count	Ipilimumab	59	↓ Baseline→↑ response	(Gebhardt et al, 2015)
Eosinophil count	Ipilimumab	209	↑ Baseline→↑ OS	(Martens et al, 2016a)
	Ipilimumab	59	↑ At week 3 vs baseline→↑ response	(Gebhardt et al, 2015)
	Ipilimumab	73	↑ At week 6 vs baseline→↑ OS	(Delyon et al, 2013)
Relative eosinophil count	Pembrolizumab	616	↑ Baseline→↑ OS	(Weide et al, 2016)
Neutrophil count	Ipilimumab	59	↓ Baseline→↑ response	(Gebhardt et al, 2015)
	Ipilimumab	720	↓ Baseline→↑ PFS and OS	(Ferrucci et al, 2016)
	Nivolumab	98	<4000 per µl at week 3–6→↑ OS	(Nakamura et al, 2016)
Neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio	Ipilimumab	58, 185	↓ Baseline→↑ OS	(Khoja et al, 2016; Zaragoza et al, 2016)
	Ipilimumab	187	↓ Baseline→↑ PFS and OS	(Ferrucci et al, 2015)
Derived neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio	Ipilimumab	720	↓ Baseline→↑ PFS and OS	(Ferrucci et al, 2016)
Monocyte count	Ipilimumab	209	↓ Baseline→↑ OS	(Martens et al, 2016a)
Lactate dehydrogenase	Ipilimumab	209, 73, 166, 58, 113, 183	↓ Baseline→↑ OS	(Delyon et al, 2013; Kelderman et al, 2014; Valpione et al, 2015; Collins and Le Manach, 2016; Dick et al, 2016; Khoja et al, 2016; Zaragoza et al, 2016; Martens et al, 2016a)
	Nivolumab	98	↑ Baseline→↓ OS	(Nakamura et al, 2016)
	Pembrolizumab	616	↓ Baseline→↑ OS	(Weide et al, 2016)
	Pembrolizumab, nivolumab	66	↓ Baseline→↑ OS ↑ At week 12 vs baseline→ ↓ Response, OS	(Diem et al, 2016)

	Ipilimumab	95	↓ At week 12→↑ response and OS	(Simeone et al, 2014)
C-reactive protein	Ipilimumab	95	↓ At week 12→↑ response and OS	(Simeone et al, 2014)
Smoking status	Nivolumab	88	Current/former smokers→↑ response	(Hellmann et al, 2014)
ECOG PS	Nivolumab	98	<1 at baseline→↑ OS	(Nakamura et al, 2016)
irAE	Ipilimumab	139	Early irAE→↑ response	(Downey et al, 2007)
	Ipilimumab	298	No association with OS	(Horvat et al, 2015)
	Nivolumab	576	Any-grade AE→↑ response	(Weber et al, 2017)
	Nivolumab	148	Rash, vitiligo and any grade AE→↑ OS	(Freeman-Keller et al, 2016)
	Pembrolizumab	67	Vitiligo→↑ objective response	(Hua et al, 2016)
	Immunotherapy	322	vitiligo-like depigmentation→↑OS	(Teulings et al, 2015)

Abbreviations: ECOG PS=Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group Performance Status; ICI=immune checkpoint inhibitor, irAE=immune-related adverse events; NSCLC=non-small-cell lung cancer; OS=overall survival; PFS=progression-free survival. Derived neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio=Absolute neutrophil count/(total leucocyte count–absolute neutrophil count).

8.1.2. Toxicity

We have found several clinical studies and reviews that have investigated biomarkers, blood markers or clinical markers related to immunotherapy-induced toxicity.

The CheckMate067 study describes a significantly higher incidence of irAEs in combined immunotherapy compared to Anti-PD1 monotherapy.

Verheijden et al. found more advanced disease to be associated with a lower rate of severe irAEs: “patients with non-lung visceral metastases (stage IV M1c or higher) less often experienced severe irAEs (11%) compared with patients with only lung and/or lymph node/soft tissue involvement (stage IV M1b or lower; 19%; adjusted risk ratio (RRadj) 0.63; 95% CI 0.41 to 0.94)”. (Verheijden et al., 2020)

Valpione et al. found a significant association between female sex and higher risk of severe toxicity. (Valpione et al., 2018) Another study specifically found female sex to be significantly associated with the development of hepatitis. In addition, this study found combined therapy to be associated with colitis, increased total and relative monocytes at baseline with development of pancreatitis. In addition, pre-existing autoimmune diseases were associated with the occurrence of irAEs. (Wölffer et al., 2022)

Body composition parameters sarcopenia and low muscle attenuation at baseline were associated with severe treatment-related toxicity to ipilimumab by Daly et al (n=84). (Daly et al., 2017)

A study done by Kartolo et al., with a mixed population have found several factors with statistically significant associations with irAE incidence; rates of steroid use before immunotherapy, sex, a history of autoimmune disease, immunotherapy with a CTLA-4 monoclonal antibody, and abnormal kidney function. However, this study was executed with a small, mixed study population treated with either ipilimumab, nivolumab and pembrolizumab (n=78, 70% melanoma, 22% non-small-cell lung cancer, 8% renal cell carcinoma). (Kartolo et al., 2018)

In a clinical practice guideline on management of immunotherapy-induced toxicities, constructed by Champiat et al., with collaboration of a network of organ specialists, the following potential irAE risk factors have been described: personal and family history of autoimmune disorders, tumor infiltration and location, previous viral infections such as HIV or hepatitis and the use of medicines with known autoimmune toxicities such as antiarrhythmics, antibiotics, anticonvulsants or antipsychotics. (Champiat et al., 2016)

Hommes et al. provide an overview of 35 articles on potential immune-related adverse event (irAE) biomarkers at baseline and during treatment, including cellular, cytokines/chemokines, autoantibodies, immunogenetics, and microbiome biomarkers. (Hommes et al., 2021). The summary is provided in Table 8.1.2

Table 8.1.2. Summary of preliminary evidence of routinely available blood and clinical markers predictive of ICI toxicity.

Potential biomarker	Determinant	Results	Cancer type	n	Treatment	Study design
Eosinophils	Peripheral blood cell counts	Eosinophil count of >240/ml associated with endocrine (but not any) irAEs	Advanced melanoma	44	Anti-PD-1	Retrospective cohort
Lymphocytes	Myeloid and T cell subsets by flow cytometry	Lower % PD-1 expression on CD4+ and CD8+ T cells associated with grade ≥3 irAEs	Metastatic melanoma	44	Anti-CTLA4	Retrospective cohort
	CD4+ T cells and Treg cells counts at baseline	Lower percentage of Tregs associated with colitis	Metastatic melanoma	18	Anti-CTLA4	Retrospective cohort
IL-6	5 cytokines and lymphocyte subsets	Lower IL-6 levels associated with grade ≥3 irAEs	Metastatic melanoma	140	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort
IL-17	Multiplex serum testing for 36 different cytokines and chemokines	Higher IL-17 levels associated with grade ≥3 colitis and grade ≥3 irAEs	Advanced melanoma	35	Anti-CTLA4	Clinical trial
Various cytokines/chemokines	65 cytokines/ chemokines profiles; validated in separate cohort	CYTOX score (G-CSF, GMCSF, fractalkine, FGF-2, IFNα2, IL1a, IL1B, IL1RA, IL2, IL12p70 and IL13) associated with irAEs that required ICI discontinuation or immunosuppression	Melanoma	49	Anti-PD-1 or combination	Prospective cohort
Various autoantibodies	Autoantibodies tested with HuProt array covering >19,000 proteins	Enrichment of autoantibodies directed against targets in (auto) immunity pathways associated with grade ≥3 irAEs Classification model based on baseline antibody levels predicts risk of developing severe irAEs	Melanoma	75	Anti-CTLA4, anti-PD1, combination	Prospective cohort

Microbiome Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes	Microbiome composition in fecal samples using 16S rRNA and shotgun metagenomic sequencing	Enrichment of Bacteroidetes in patients without colitis. Lack of pathways involved in vitamin B synthesis associated with increased colitis risk	Melanoma	34	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort
	Microbiome composition in fecal samples using 16S rRNA sequencing	Enrichment of Bacteroidetes in patients without colitis. Enrichment of Firmicutes in patients with colitis	Melanoma	26	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort
Thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH)	Serum TSH	TSH >2.19 μ U/ml associated with increased risk of thyroid dysfunction	Melanoma	99	Anti-PD-1, combination	Retrospective cohort
Soluble CTLA-4	sCTLA-4 in serum by ELISA	>200 pg/ml sCTLA-4 associated with irAEs	Melanoma	113	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort

8.1.3. References

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8.2. Annex 2 - Integration of publications summaries in the physician DSS

In this Annex, we show a possible way of integrating reports with summaries of most recent publications into the physician DSS. These summaries are about clinical factors that can affect survival, response, and toxicity. Reviewing these summaries can help physicians in their decisions regarding the right treatment for specific patients. In the screen captions below we demonstrated how we can integrate report from **Annex 1**. The captions below show the way of accessing the summary using the navigation thru the interface menu. The window that presents the summary content for both cases (overall response and toxicity) is a mockup that imagines the way of presentation by a group of separate windows with text and table

ID: 890438
Maria De Rossi
 1944 Nov 10 (76 y.o.)

GUIDELINES | RUN PREDICTIVE MODEL | SCHEDULE NEXT VISIT | PRESCRIBE NEW TREATMENT

Treatment | Measurement

Questionnaire results | Symptoms | Lab tests | Achievements

Current | Past

Treatment for cancer

Systemic therapy
 Sunitinib 50 mg/2 weeks, hospital admin. (12)

Surgery
 12 October 2018

Radiotherapy
 12 December 2018 – 22 December 2018

Treatment for comorbidities | PRESCRIBED VIA EHR
 Levotyroxine (23 March 2017)
 Hypothyroidism

Treatment of adverse events | PRESCRIBED VIA EHR
 Loperamide 4 mg/4 hours, As needed medication
 Diarrhea

Skin Toxicity
 Diarrhea
 Fatigue
 Immune-related skin toxicity
 Gastrointestinal toxicity

Beyond the guidelines

Treatment of Diarrhea
Uncomplicated diarrhea initial management
 Initial management of mild to moderate diarrhea

Predictors for **survival and response** for Melanoma patients treated with ICI

Predictors for **toxicity** for Melanoma patients treated with ICI

Treatment of Diarrhea
Consider other drugs
 After 48 hours, in case of absence of efficacy of loperamide, administration of other drugs should be considered.

REVIEW

Treatment of Cutaneous Melanoma
 Nivolumab 240 ma IV a2Weeks

ID: 890438
Maria De Rossi
 1944 Nov 10 (76 y.o.)

GUIDELINES | RUN PREDICTIVE MODEL | SCHEDULE NEXT VISIT | PRESCRIBE NEW TREATMENT

Treatment | Measurement

Questionnaire results | Symptoms | Lab tests | Achievements

Current | Past

Treatment for cancer

Systemic therapy
 Sunitinib 50 mg/2 weeks, hospital admin. (12)

Surgery
 12 October 2018

Radiotherapy
 12 December 2018 – 22 December 2018

Treatment for comorbidities | PRESCRIBED VIA EHR
 Levotyroxine (23 March 2017)
 Hypothyroidism

Treatment of adverse events | PRESCRIBED VIA EHR
 Loperamide 4 mg/4 hours, As needed medication
 Diarrhea

Skin Toxicity
 Diarrhea
 Fatigue
 Immune-related skin toxicity
 Gastrointestinal toxicity

Beyond the guidelines

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Uncomplicated diarrhea initial management
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Predictors for **survival and response** for Melanoma patients treated with ICI

Predictors for **toxicity** for Melanoma patients treated with ICI

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Consider other drugs
 After 48 hours, in case of absence of efficacy of loperamide, administration of other drugs should be considered.

REVIEW

Treatment of Cutaneous Melanoma
 Nivolumab 240 ma IV a2Weeks

ID: 890438

Overall survival/response
 Several studies have shown a correlation between toxicity and ICI response. (Eggermont et al., 2020; Okada et al., 2019). It is suggested that clinical response improves with irAE occurrence.

Hopkins et al. conducted a literature review on routinely available blood and clinical markers associated with treatment between a range of factors lymphocyte count and in overall survival. A lower was associated with imp baseline were associated week 12 vs. baseline we at baseline was associate AEs, or specifically rash shows a Table from Hopk et al., 2017)

A retrospective analysis melanoma confirmed by ECOG PS 0, and objective survival. For progressive response were found to overall survival decrease. These results are similar ECOG PS 0 as adverse f was negatively associate

Table 1 Table from (Hopkins et al., 2017) Summary of preliminary evidence of routinely available blood and clinical markers predictive of ICI outcomes.

Marker	ICI therapy	N	Study results	Reference
Lymphocyte count	Ipilimumab	51, 73	>1000 per µl at week 6 → ↑ OS	(Delyon et al, 2013; Ku et al, 2010)
	Ipilimumab	82, 40	↑ At 2-8 weeks vs baseline → ↑ response	(Bjorn et al, 2016; Martens et al, 2016b)
	Ipilimumab	95	↑ At week 12 vs baseline → ↑ OS	(Simeone et al, 2014)
Relative lymphocyte count	Nivolumab	98	>1000 per µl at week 3-6 → ↑ OS	(Nakamura et al, 2016)
	Ipilimumab	209	↑ Baseline → ↑ OS	(Martens et al, 2016a)
Total leucocyte count	Pembrolizumab	616	↑ Baseline → ↑ OS	(Weide et al, 2016)
	Ipilimumab	59	↓ Baseline → ↑ response	(Gebhardt et al, 2015)
Eosinophil count	Ipilimumab	209	↑ Baseline → ↑ OS	(Martens et al, 2016a)
	Ipilimumab	59	↑ At week 3 vs baseline → ↑ response	(Gebhardt et al, 2015)
	Ipilimumab	73	↑ At week 6 vs baseline → ↑ OS	(Delyon et al, 2013)
Relative eosinophil count	Pembrolizumab	616	↑ Baseline → ↑ OS	(Weide et al, 2016)
Neutrophil count	Ipilimumab	59	↓ Baseline → ↑ response	(Gebhardt et al, 2015)
	Ipilimumab	720	↓ Baseline → ↑ PFS and OS	(Ferrucci et al, 2016)
	Nivolumab	98	<4000 per µl at week 3-6 → ↑ OS	(Nakamura et al, 2016)
Neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio	Ipilimumab	58, 185	↓ Baseline → ↑ OS	(Khoja et al, 2016; Zaragoza et al, 2016)
	Ipilimumab	187	↓ Baseline → ↑ PFS and OS	(Ferrucci et al, 2015)
Derived neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio	Ipilimumab	720	↓ Baseline → ↑ PFS and OS	(Ferrucci et al, 2016)
Monocyte count	Ipilimumab	209	↑ Baseline → ↑ OS	(Martens et al, 2016a)
Lactate dehydrogenase	Ipilimumab	209, 73, 166, 58, 113, 183	↓ Baseline → ↑ OS	(Delyon et al, 2013; Kelderman et al, 2014; Valpione et al, 2015; Collins and Le Manach, 2016; Dick et al, 2016; Khoja et al, 2016; Zaragoza et al, 2016; Martens et al, 2016a)

Treatment of Cutaneous melanoma
 Nivolumab 240 mg IV q2Weeks

ID: 890438

Maria De Rossi
 1944 Nov 10 (76 y.o)

GUIDELINES | RUN PREDICTIVE MODEL | SCHEDULE NEXT VISIT | PRESCRIBE NEW TREATMENT

Treatment | Measurement | Questionnaire results | Symptoms | Lab tests | Achievements

Current | Past

Treatment for cancer

Systemic therapy
 Sunitinib 50 mg/2 weeks, hospital admin. (12 October 2018)

Surgery
 12 October 2018

Radiotherapy
 12 December 2018 – 22 December 2018

Treatment for comorbidities | PRESCRIBED VIA EHR
 Levotyroxine (23 March 2017)
 Hypothyroidism

Treatment of adverse events | PRESCRIBED VIA EHR
 Loperamide 4 mg/4 hours, As needed medication
 Diarrhea

Treatment of Diarrhea
Uncomplicated diarrhea initial management
 Initial management of mild to moderate diarrhea
 Predictors for survival and response for Melanoma patients treated with ICI
 Predictors for toxicity for Melanoma patients treated with ICI

Treatment of Diarrhea
Consider other drugs
 After 48 hours, in case of absence of efficacy of loperamide, administration of other drugs should be considered.
 REVIEW

Treatment of Cutaneous Melanoma
 Nivolumab 240 mg IV q2Weeks

ID: 890438

Toxicity

We have found several clinical studies and reviews that have investigated biomarkers, blood markers or clinical markers related to immunotherapy-induced toxicity.

The CheckMate067 study describes a significantly higher incidence of irAEs in combined immunotherapy compared to Anti-PD1 monotherapy.

Verheijden et al. found more advanced disease to be associated with a lower rate of severe irAEs: "patients with non-lung visceral metastases (stage IV M1c or higher) less often experienced severe irAEs (11%) compared with patients with only lung and/or lymph node/soft tissue involvement (95% CI 0.41 to 0.94)".

Valpione et al. found a toxicity, (Valpione et al. associated with the development of pancre with the occurrence of

Body composition parameters associated with severe al., 2017)

A study done by Kartolo statistically significant immunotherapy, sex, a monoclonal antibody, a small, mixed study pembrolizumab (n=78, carcinoma). (Kartolo et al., 2019)

Table 2. Table from (Hommès et al., 2021) Summary of preliminary evidence of routinely available blood and clinical markers predictive of ICI toxicity.

Potential biomarker	Determinant	Results	Cancer type	n	Treatment	Study design	Reference
Eosinophils	Peripheral blood cell counts	Eosinophil count of >240/ml associated with endocrine (but not any) irAEs	Advanced melanoma	44	Anti-PD-1	Retrospective cohort	
T lymphocytes	Myeloid and T cell subsets by flow cytometry	Lower % PD-1 expression on CD4+ and CD8+ T cells associated with grade ≥3 irAEs	Metastatic melanoma	44	Anti-CTLA4	Retrospective cohort	
	CD4+ T cells and Treg cells counts at baseline	Lower percentage of Tregs associated with colitis	Metastatic melanoma	18	Anti-CTLA4	Retrospective cohort	
IL-6	5 cytokines and lymphocyte subsets	Lower IL-6 levels associated with grade ≥3 irAEs	Metastatic melanoma	140	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort	
IL-17	Multiple serum testing for 36 different cytokines and chemokines	Higher IL-17 levels associated with grade ≥3 colitis and grade ≥3 irAEs	Advanced melanoma	35	Anti-CTLA4	Clinical trial	
Various cytokines/chemokines	65 cytokines/chemokines profiles, validated in separate cohort	CYTUX score (C-CSF, GM-CSF, fractalkine, FGF-2, IFN- γ , IL-1 α , IL-1 β , IL-1 δ , IL-2, IL-10/7 β and IL-13) associated with irAEs that require ICI discontinuation or immunosuppression	Melanoma	49	Anti-PD-1 or combination	Prospective cohort	(26)
Various autoantibodies	Autoantibodies tested with HiFiNot array covering >19,000 proteins	Enrichment of autoantibodies directed against targets in (auto) immunity pathways associated with grade ≥3 irAEs. Classification model based on baseline antibody levels predicts risk of developing severe irAEs	Melanoma	75	Anti-CTLA4, anti-PD-1, combination	Prospective cohort	
Microbiome Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes	Microbiome composition in fecal samples using 16S rRNA and shotgun metagenomic sequencing	Enrichment of Bacteroidetes in patients without colitis. Lack of pathways involved in vitamin B synthesis associated with increased colitis risk	Melanoma	34	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort	
	Microbiome composition in fecal samples using 16S rRNA sequencing	Enrichment of Bacteroidetes in patients without colitis. Enrichment of Firmicutes in patients with colitis	Melanoma	26	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort	
Thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH)	Serum TSH	TSH >2.10 μ U/ml associated with increased risk of thyroid dysfunction	Melanoma	99	Anti-PD-1, combination	Retrospective cohort	
Soluble CTLA-4	sCTLA-4 in serum by ELISA	>200 pg/ml sCTLA-4 associated with irAEs	Melanoma	113	Anti-CTLA4	Prospective cohort	

Treatment of Cutaneous Melanoma

8.3. Annex 3 - Predicting Renal Cancer - Exploratory Research

Renal cancer is one of the most common cancers, especially among elderly and multimorbidity patients. The impacts of renal cancer are vast and span from general treatment costs to increased patient treatment load. There are many possible causes that include genetic conditions, demographic variables such as age and gender, lifestyle choices like consumption of alcohol or tobacco as well as obesity, environmental factors that include contaminating agents such as cadmium and comorbidities. In this work, we focus on comorbidities that may serve as a contributing factor to renal cancer some are known (e.g., hypertension, chronic kidney disease, cancer of the bladder,) and others are suspected to be associated with the condition (e.g., retinopathy that is in fact caused by chronic kidney disease).

In order to gauge the current state of the art regarding kidney cancer prediction, we conducted a literature review and found circa 40 relevant papers. Previous studies on prediction of kidney cancer focused mostly on biomarkers and environmental factors / lifestyle, which may introduce bias since tobacco and alcohol consumption as well as environmental contamination has been linked more often to specific socio-economic levels that may have different access to healthcare and different quality of life than other socio-economic levels. Additionally, most models focused on predicting present kidney cancer by examining the patient's symptoms.

The main goal of this project is to predict whether a patient will be diagnosed in the future with kidney cancer, based on the patient's comorbidities. This will provide an opportunity for a 6-month minimum window so that crucial screening can begin and the condition can be managed as soon as possible.

We extracted patient data using ICD9 and ICD10 codes from the MarketScan database. Two types of patients were retrieved: renal patients that had diagnosis codes and categories in their record related to renal cancer (e.g., 209.24 Malignant carcinoid tumor of the kidney) and non-renal patients that were retrieved by excluding those same codes and categories. The age of the patients was limited to 18-90 years. Each patient had at least 2.5 years of enrollment which allowed us to collect comorbidities starting 2.5 years before the renal cancer diagnosis until 6 months before the diagnosis, thus showing what comorbidities were present up to 6 months before the condition. The comorbidities were extracted with a list of over 630 ICD9 and ICD10 codes.

The extraction resulted in 11K renal patients (that had the diagnosis codes and categories for renal cancer in their record) and 22K non-renal patients. We trained multiple machine learning algorithms on the data (XGBoost, Random forest, Logistic regression, K-neighbors, SVM) and combined them for ensemble learning. We also performed a Univariate analysis and SHAP analysis (see **Figure 8.3.1**) that have confirmed the findings in the literature and presented comorbidities such as chronic kidney disease and hypertension as very important. The Accuracy of the XGBoost classifier was 0.69 with an AUC of 0.68.

Figure 8.3.1 SHAP analysis of XGBoost confirming the comorbidities mentioned in the literature.

8.4. Annex 4 - Outcomes of the demonstration of 3-year survival prediction for mRCC patients

Table 8.4.1. Descriptive Statistics of RCC patients

Characteristic	Total, N = 322 ¹	Train, N = 257 ¹	Hold-Out, N = 65 ¹	p-value ²
Gender				0.96
Male	252 (78%)	201 (78%)	51 (78%)	
Female	70 (22%)	56 (22%)	14 (22%)	
Age at diagnosis				0.56
< 65	254 (79%)	201 (78%)	53 (82%)	
>= 65	68 (21%)	56 (22%)	12 (18%)	
BMI group				0.94
Normal	136 (42%)	109 (42%)	27 (42%)	
Overweight	155 (48%)	124 (48%)	31 (48%)	
Obese	31 (9.6%)	24 (9.3%)	7 (11%)	
Karnofsky PS				0.38
80	17 (5.3%)	13 (5.1%)	4 (6.2%)	
90	57 (18%)	42 (16%)	15 (23%)	
100	248 (77%)	202 (79%)	46 (71%)	
T stage				0.26
T1	45 (15%)	35 (14%)	10 (17%)	
T2	66 (21%)	49 (20%)	17 (28%)	
T3	189 (62%)	158 (64%)	31 (52%)	
T4	7 (2.3%)	5 (2.0%)	2 (3.3%)	
Unknown	15	10	5	
M stage				0.15
M0	202 (63%)	167 (65%)	35 (54%)	
M1	61 (19%)	48 (19%)	13 (20%)	
MX	59 (18%)	42 (16%)	17 (26%)	
N stage				0.90
N0	168 (52%)	132 (51%)	36 (55%)	
N1	37 (11%)	30 (12%)	7 (11%)	
N2	13 (4.0%)	10 (3.9%)	3 (4.6%)	
NX	104 (32%)	85 (33%)	19 (29%)	
Tumor Size				0.72
0-40 mm	15 (4.8%)	12 (4.8%)	3 (4.8%)	
40-70 mm	94 (30%)	78 (31%)	16 (25%)	
70-100 mm	126 (40%)	97 (38%)	29 (46%)	
> 100 mm	80 (25%)	65 (26%)	15 (24%)	
Unknown	7	5	2	
Fuhrman Grade				0.41
Grade I	5 (1.6%)	3 (1.2%)	2 (3.3%)	
Grade II	103 (34%)	81 (33%)	22 (37%)	
Grade III	121 (39%)	97 (39%)	24 (40%)	
Grade IV	78 (25%)	66 (27%)	12 (20%)	
Unknown	15	10	5	
Microvascular Invasion	128 (42%)	103 (42%)	25 (42%)	>0.99
Unknown	15	10	5	
Intra-Tumoral Necrosis	194 (63%)	158 (64%)	36 (60%)	0.57
Unknown	15	10	5	

Table 8.4.1. Descriptive Statistics of RCC patients

Characteristic	Total, N = 322 ¹	Train, N = 257 ¹	Hold-Out, N = 65 ¹	p-value ²
Clear Cell Carcinoma	289 (90%)	231 (90%)	58 (89%)	0.88
Sarcomatoid Feature	83 (26%)	70 (27%)	13 (20%)	0.23
Unknown	1	1	0	
Kidney Metastases	56 (17%)	46 (18%)	10 (15%)	0.63
Lymphnodes Metastases	145 (45%)	119 (46%)	26 (40%)	0.36
Lung Metastases	235 (73%)	184 (72%)	51 (78%)	0.27
Brain Metastases	15 (4.7%)	11 (4.3%)	4 (6.2%)	0.51
Liver Metastases	59 (18%)	50 (19%)	9 (14%)	0.30
Bone Metastases	69 (21%)	51 (20%)	18 (28%)	0.17
Hemoglobin g/dl	13.8 (12.7, 14.7)	13.8 (12.7, 14.6)	13.9 (12.5, 15.1)	0.69
Serum Corr. Calcium mg/dl	9.8 (9.3, 10.1)	9.8 (9.3, 10.1)	9.8 (9.5, 10.1)	0.68
LDH mU/ml	233.0 (199.2, 315.0)	232.0 (200.0, 310.0)	235.0 (199.0, 337.0)	0.47
Serum Sodium (Na) mmol/l	141.0 (139.0, 144.0)	141.0 (139.0, 144.0)	142.0 (140.0, 144.0)	0.11
Creatinine	1.1 (0.9, 1.3)	1.1 (0.9, 1.3)	1.2 (1.0, 1.3)	0.069
PLR	170.3 (123.7, 218.2)	170.6 (124.0, 215.0)	168.2 (122.2, 240.0)	0.53
NLR	3.5 (2.8, 4.2)	3.5 (2.9, 4.2)	3.5 (2.6, 4.5)	0.74
Prior Interferon Treatment	85 (26%)	66 (26%)	19 (29%)	0.56
Treatment - 1st line				0.34
Chemo	15 (4.7%)	14 (5.4%)	1 (1.5%)	
Immunotherapy	7 (2.2%)	5 (1.9%)	2 (3.1%)	
Targeted	300 (93%)	238 (93%)	62 (95%)	
Months from Dx to 1st line	12.8 (3.7, 49.6)	12.4 (3.9, 47.1)	12.9 (3.6, 56.0)	0.92
Days from Dx to Surgery	19.0 (10.0, 32.0)	18.0 (10.0, 32.0)	20.5 (10.0, 37.0)	0.85
Unknown	15	10	5	
Toxicity - 1st line	116 (36%)	90 (35%)	26 (40%)	0.45
Dose Reduction - 1st line	98 (30%)	75 (29%)	23 (35%)	0.33
Best Response - 1st line				0.18
Complete Response	10 (3.1%)	9 (3.5%)	1 (1.5%)	
Partial Response	117 (36%)	95 (37%)	22 (34%)	
Stable Disease	160 (50%)	130 (51%)	30 (46%)	
Progressive Disease	35 (11%)	23 (8.9%)	12 (18%)	

¹n (%); Median (IQR)

²Pearson's Chi-squared test; Fisher's exact test; Wilcoxon rank sum test

Table 8.4.2. Univariate Analysis			
Characteristic	Survivors, N = 125¹	Non-Survivors, N = 197¹	p-value²
Months from Dx to 1st line	31.9 (7.9, 86.1)	9.4 (3.2, 29.4)	<0.001
Days from Dx to Surgery	17.0 (8.0, 28.0)	21.0 (10.2, 36.0)	0.067
Unknown	4	11	
Treatment - 1st line			0.25
Chemo	8 (6.4%)	7 (3.6%)	
Immunotherapy	1 (0.8%)	6 (3.0%)	
Targeted	116 (93%)	184 (93%)	
Gender			0.18
Male	93 (74%)	159 (81%)	
Female	32 (26%)	38 (19%)	
Age at diagnosis			<0.001
< 65	111 (89%)	143 (73%)	
>= 65	14 (11%)	54 (27%)	
BMI group			0.039
Normal	42 (34%)	94 (48%)	
Overweight	68 (54%)	87 (44%)	
Obese	15 (12%)	16 (8.1%)	
Karnofsky PS			<0.001
80	0 (0%)	17 (8.6%)	
90	6 (4.8%)	51 (26%)	
100	119 (95%)	129 (65%)	
T stage			0.038
T1	17 (14%)	28 (15%)	
T2	36 (30%)	30 (16%)	
T3	66 (55%)	123 (66%)	
T4	2 (1.7%)	5 (2.7%)	
Unknown	4	11	
M stage			<0.001
M0	90 (72%)	112 (57%)	
M1	9 (7.2%)	52 (26%)	
MX	26 (21%)	33 (17%)	
N stage			0.68
N0	68 (54%)	100 (51%)	
N1	11 (8.8%)	26 (13%)	
N2	5 (4.0%)	8 (4.1%)	
NX	41 (33%)	63 (32%)	
Tumor Size			0.009
0-40 mm	4 (3.2%)	11 (5.8%)	
40-70 mm	44 (35%)	50 (26%)	
70-100 mm	56 (45%)	70 (37%)	
> 100 mm	20 (16%)	60 (31%)	
Unknown	1	6	
Fuhrman Grade			<0.001
Grade I	2 (1.7%)	3 (1.6%)	
Grade II	56 (46%)	47 (25%)	

Table 8.4.2. Univariate Analysis			
Characteristic	Survivors, N = 125¹	Non-Survivors, N = 197¹	p-value²
Grade III	46 (38%)	75 (40%)	
Grade IV	17 (14%)	61 (33%)	
Unknown	4	11	
Microvascular Invasion	38 (31%)	90 (48%)	0.003
Unknown	4	11	
Intra-Tumoral Necrosis	66 (55%)	128 (69%)	0.011
Unknown	4	11	
Clear Cell Carcinoma	113 (90%)	176 (89%)	0.76
Sarcomatoid Feature	17 (14%)	66 (34%)	<0.001
Unknown	0	1	
Kidney Metastases	28 (22%)	28 (14%)	0.059
Lymphnodes Metastases	45 (36%)	100 (51%)	0.009
Lung Metastases	81 (65%)	154 (78%)	0.008
Brain Metastases	2 (1.6%)	13 (6.6%)	0.038
Liver Metastases	17 (14%)	42 (21%)	0.081
Bone Metastases	19 (15%)	50 (25%)	0.030
Hemoglobin g/dl	14.1 (13.1, 14.9)	13.5 (12.5, 14.4)	<0.001
Serum Corr. Calcium mg/dl	9.7 (9.2, 10.1)	9.8 (9.4, 10.3)	0.011
LDH mU/ml	210.0 (188.0, 250.0)	256.0 (212.0, 362.0)	<0.001
PLR	148.1 (120.6, 205.0)	178.5 (126.5, 233.3)	0.006
NLR	3.3 (2.7, 4.0)	3.5 (3.0, 4.4)	0.010
Serum Sodium(Na) mmol/l	141.0 (139.0, 144.0)	141.0 (139.0, 144.0)	0.10
Creatinine	1.1 (0.9, 1.3)	1.1 (1.0, 1.3)	0.036
¹ Median (IQR); n (%)			
² Wilcoxon rank sum test; Fisher's exact test; Pearson's Chi-squared test			

Table 8.4.3. Survival Analysis					
	Kaplan-Meier		COX		
Characteristic	3-year OS (%)	p-value¹	HR²	95% CI²	p-value
Gender		0.12			
Male	36.9		—	—	
Female	45.7		0.81	0.61, 1.06	0.13
Age at diagnosis		<0.001			
< 65	43.7		—	—	
≥ 65	20.6		1.69	1.28, 2.24	<0.001
T stage		0.094			
T1	37.8		—	—	
T2	54.5		0.71	0.48, 1.05	0.088
T3	34.9		1.03	0.74, 1.43	0.86
T4	28.6		1.06	0.44, 2.53	0.89
N stage		0.8			
N0	40.5		—	—	
N1	29.7		1.01	0.70, 1.47	0.95
N2	38.5		1.05	0.60, 1.86	0.86
NX	39.4		1.12	0.87, 1.44	0.38
M stage		<0.001			
M0	44.6		—	—	
M1	14.8		2.27	1.69, 3.06	<0.001
MX	44.1		1.19	0.88, 1.60	0.26
Tumor Size		0.029			
0-40 mm	26.7		—	—	
40-70 mm	46.8		0.66	0.38, 1.15	0.14
70-100 mm	44.4		0.66	0.38, 1.12	0.12
> 100 mm	25.0		0.95	0.55, 1.66	0.87
Fuhrman Grade		<0.001			
Grade I	40.0		—	—	
Grade II	54.4		0.48	0.20, 1.19	0.11
Grade III	38.0		0.60	0.24, 1.47	0.27
Grade IV	21.8		0.90	0.37, 2.24	0.83
Microvascular Invasion		0.046			
No	46.4		—	—	
Yes	29.7		1.27	1.00, 1.60	0.047
Intra-Tumoral Necrosis		0.017			
No	48.7		—	—	
Yes	34.0		1.34	1.05, 1.70	0.017
Clear Cell Carcinoma		0.5			
No	36.4		—	—	
Yes	39.1		0.89	0.62, 1.28	0.54
Sarcomatoid Feature		<0.001			
No	45.4		—	—	
Yes	20.5		1.70	1.31, 2.20	<0.001
Prior Interferon Treatment		0.14			
No	35.0		—	—	

Table 8.4.3. Survival Analysis					
	Kaplan-Meier		COX		
Characteristic	3-year OS (%)	p-value¹	HR²	95% CI²	p-value
Yes	49.4		0.83	0.64, 1.07	0.14
Treatment - First line		0.007			
Chemo	53.3		—	—	
Immunotherapy	14.3		3.75	1.52, 9.28	0.004
Targeted	38.7		1.24	0.74, 2.09	0.41
BMI group		0.10			
Normal	30.9		—	—	
Overweight	43.9		0.79	0.62, 1.00	0.047
Obese	48.4		0.75	0.50, 1.12	0.16
Kidney Metastases		0.2			
No	36.5		—	—	
Yes	50.0		0.82	0.61, 1.10	0.18
Lymphnodes Metastases		0.039			
No	45.2		—	—	
Yes	31.0		1.27	1.01, 1.59	0.040
Lung Metastases		0.012			
No	50.6		—	—	
Yes	34.5		1.38	1.07, 1.79	0.013
Brain Metastases		0.002			
No	40.1		—	—	
Yes	13.3		2.23	1.32, 3.76	0.003
Liver Metastases		0.11			
No	41.1		—	—	
Yes	28.8		1.27	0.95, 1.70	0.11
Bone Metastases		0.005			
No	41.9		—	—	
Yes	27.5		1.48	1.13, 1.94	0.005
Karnofsky PS		<0.001			
80	—		—	—	
90	10.5		0.23	0.13, 0.40	<0.001
100	48.0		0.07	0.04, 0.13	<0.001
Hemoglobin < LLN		<0.001			
No	46.6		—	—	
Yes	10.1		3.09	2.34, 4.07	<0.001
Serum Corr. Calcium > ULN		<0.001			
No	43.0		—	—	
Yes	21.9		1.90	1.44, 2.51	<0.001
LDH > 1.5*ULN		<0.001			
No	57.8		—	—	
Yes	25.1		2.02	1.60, 2.54	<0.001
Creatinine > ULN		0.4			
No	41.7		—	—	
Yes	29.3		1.12	0.85, 1.46	0.43
Serum Sodium < LLN		<0.001			

Table 8.4.3. Survival Analysis					
	Kaplan-Meier		COX		
Characteristic	3-year OS (%)	p-value¹	HR²	95% CI²	p-value
No	39.6		—	—	
Yes	—		3.95	1.74, 8.97	0.001
High PLR		0.10			
No	47.5		—	—	
Yes	32.2		1.21	0.96, 1.52	0.11
High NLR		0.007			
No	42.9		—	—	
Yes	32.5		1.37	1.09, 1.73	0.007
¹ Log-rank test					
² HR = Hazard Ratio, CI = Confidence Interval					